

Synthesis, physical characterization of bivalent cobalt and copper complexes of 12-membered quadridentate [N₄] macrocyclic ligand

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Abstract : The structures of new cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes derived from 12-membered tetraaza macrocyclic ligand namely dibenzo-[b,g]-5,6,11,12-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-4,7-10,12-tetraene have been elucidated after their synthesis by using various physico-chemical methods viz. elemental analysis, molar conductivity measurements, solid state room temperature magnetic susceptibility, spectral (IR, electronic, mass and EPR) and thermal analysis. The IR frequencies were in accordance with *d-d* absorption frequencies. IR spectra suggested that ligand was coordinated to the metal ion in a tetradentate fashion through azomethine nitrogen atoms. The *g* values were calculated from EPR spectra for Cu^{II} complexes indicated the presence of the unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The electronic spectra suggest an octahedral and tetragonal structure around Co^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ion respectively. Electrochemical behavior of the complex [CuLCl₂] has also been discussed. TG studies suggested the absence of water molecules inside or outside the coordination sphere.

Keywords : Macrocyclic, octahedral, spectroscopic, magnetic moment, anisotropic, tetragonal.

Introduction

The synthesis of macrocyclic complexes has been a fascinating area of research and growing at a very fast pace owing to their analytical, industrial and medicinal applications^{1,2}. Nature prefers macrocyclic derivatives for many fundamental biological functions like photosynthesis and transport of oxygen in respiratory system³. The complexation capabilities of polyazamacrocycles are mainly governed by ring size⁴. The importance of macrocyclic complexes in coordination chemistry is because of its resemblance with many natural systems like porphyrins and cobalamines⁵. Schiff base macrocyclic ligands are of significant interest not only for their wide biological properties as antibacterial, anti-cancer, antiviral and antifungal agents⁶⁻⁸, but also for their capacity for chemical recognition of anions and metals of biochemical and environmental importance⁹. The chemistry of macrocyclic complexes is also important due to their use as dyes and pigments as well as NMR shift reagent^{10,11}. In the light

of above applications the present paper reports the structurally characterized cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes with dibenzo-[b,g]-5,6,11,12-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-4,7-10,12-tetraene.

Experimental

All chemicals of analytical reagent grade quality were used without further purification.

Instrumentation :

The C, H and N were analyzed on Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Elico (CM82T) conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature on Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. IR spectra (4000–200 cm⁻¹) (KBr and CsI) were recorded on FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. EPR spectra of complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample on E₄-EPR spectrometer. Electronic

impact mass spectrum was recorded on Jeol, JMS-DX-303 mass spectrometer. The cyclic voltammetric experiments were performed on a PAR model 273 potentiostat coupled to a PAR model 175 universal programmer. The thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on Shimadzu TQA-50 H thermal analyzer.

General procedure : Synthesis of complexes :

A template reaction was carried out to synthesize the complexes. A hot EtOH solution (20 ml) of the respective divalent metal salt (10 mmol) was mixed with a hot solution (20 ml) of *o*-phenylenediamine (20 mmol) in the same solvent. Then an EtOH solution (20 ml) of 2,3-butanedione (20 mmol) in the presence of a few drops of conc. HCl was added to the resultant solution and the reaction mixture was left under reflux for about 3–4 h as appropriate. The complexes were precipitated out on cooling the solution overnight. They were collected by filtration, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. The general reaction for the formation of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is given in Scheme 1.

Results and discussion

The general composition for all the complexes was found MLX₂, where M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SCN⁻. All the complexes provided satisfactory C, H and N results (Table 1) which were in good agreement with those calculated for the suggested formulae. The complexes were variously coloured, polycrystalline solids, air stable and insoluble in water and common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO and DMF.

Molar conductance measurement :

Complexes were dissolved in DMF and molar conductivities of 10⁻³ M of their solutions at room temperature were measured. It is concluded from the results that complexes have small conductance (12–18 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) values (Table 1), indicating that they are non-electrolytes¹². The low value suggested that the anions are inside the coordination sphere and bonded to the metal ion. Therefore, these complexes may be formulated as [MLX₂]. The low value of molar conductance may be due to large size of anionic coordination sphere¹³.

Scheme 1. Template condensation between diamine and diketone in presence of divalent metal salt, where M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SCN⁻.

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of metal complexes

Complexes	Colour	Dec. temp. (°C)	Molar cond. (Ω ⁻² cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{ff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					M	C	H	N
[CoLCl ₂]	Brown	248	18	4.82	13.28	53.70	4.56	12.68
CoC ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ Cl ₂					(13.22)	(53.81)	(4.48)	(12.55)
[CoL(NO ₃) ₂]	Green	260	12	4.78	11.72	48.16	4.09	16.90
CoC ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₆					(11.82)	(48.09)	(4.00)	(16.83)
[CoL(SCN) ₂]	Reddish brown	256	15	4.88	12.19	53.83	4.18	17.24
CoC ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂					(12.01)	(53.76)	(4.07)	(17.10)
[CuLCl ₂]	Blue	252	17	1.89	14.14	53.46	4.30	12.60
CuC ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄ Cl ₂					(14.00)	(53.33)	(4.44)	(12.44)
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	Dark brown	245	13	1.76	12.65	47.65	4.20	16.82
CuC ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₆					(12.52)	(47.71)	(3.97)	(16.69)
[CuL(SCN) ₂]	Light brown	255	15	1.84	12.84	53.47	4.12	17.20
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₆ S ₂					(12.72)	(53.33)	(4.04)	(16.96)

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

The cobalt(II) complexes reported herein showed room temperature magnetic moment values in the range 4.78–4.88 B.M. (Table 1), (normal range for octahedral Co^{II} complexes is 4.3–5.2 B.M.), which was an indicative of octahedral geometry¹⁴. The experimental values were higher than spin only value due to orbital angular momentum contribution in d^7 system. On the other hand the copper(II) complexes showed magnetic moment in the range 1.76–1.89 B.M. (Table 1) corresponding to one unpaired electron within the range normally observed for six coordinated Cu^{II} complexes¹⁵. It was slightly higher than those expected for a d^9 system. This may be attributed to the incomplete quenching of the orbital contribution to the magnetic moment or to spin orbit coupling.

*Spectroscopy :**IR spectra and modes of bonding :*

IR spectral bands ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) for the complexes provided significant indication regarding the bonding sites. Selected infrared spectral bands of the complexes are given in Table 2. The absence of bands *ca.* $3400\text{--}3160\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of ν_{sym} and ν_{asym} of the free -NH_2 group confirmed the formation of macrocyclic complexes. The occurrence of a medium intensity band at *ca.* $1580\text{--}1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the imine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁷ stretching frequency was appeared at lower frequencies than free $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequency in the complexes, suggested that coordination took place through the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ moieties. The appearance of a band at *ca.* $410\text{--}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes, which was assigned to $\nu(\text{M}\text{-N})$ ¹⁸ also indicated that metal was bonded to azomethine nitrogen. Therefore, it was concluded that ligand acted in tetradentate fashion and binds to metal ions through imine nitrogen atoms.

The presence of IR spectral bands at *ca.* $1450\text{--}1430$, $1345\text{--}1290$ and $1076\text{--}1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of nitrate complexes (Fig. 1), suggested that both nitrate groups were coordinated to the central metal ion in an unidentate fashion¹⁹. Thiocyanate anion may coordinate in different ways. It can show linkage isomerism. The reported complexes showed a single sharp band at *ca.* $2120\text{--}2150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicated both thiocyanate groups were S bonded²⁰

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of complexes were recorded in

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of nitrate complex of cobalt

DMSO. The Co^{II} complexes gave three electronic spectral bands at *ca.* $8700\text{--}8772$, $18100\text{--}18621$ and $20000\text{--}20833\text{ cm}^{-1}$ wave number regions (Table 3). These bands were assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(P)$ respectively. The positions of bands indicated that Co^{II} complexes have an overall octahedral geometry²¹. The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes displayed one broad absorption band (Fig. 2) in the range $17241\text{--}14680\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 2). The e_g and t_{2g} states of octahedral Cu^{II} ion split into B_{1g} , A_{1g} , B_{2g} and E_g level under the influence of the tetragonal distortion²²

Fig. 2. Electronic spectrum of chloro complex of copper.

Table 2. IR absorption bands (cm⁻¹) of complexes

Complexes	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching (Aromatic ring)	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$
[CoLCl ₂]	1443	1565	420
[CoL(NO ₃) ₂]	1453	1550	425
[CoL(SCN) ₂]	1458	1545	410
[CuLCl ₂]	1463	1562	445
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	1459	1560	430
[CuL(SCN) ₂]	1450	1558	450

and the distortion can be such as to cause the transitions ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ to remain unresolved in the spectra²³.

EPR spectra :

EPR spectra of the Co^{II} complexes were recorded as polycrystalline samples. At room temperature no EPR signal was observed because the lattice spin relaxation of Co^{II} broadens the lines at higher temperature. The complexes showed a very broad isotropic signal at liquid nitrogen temperature. The observed g values were found in the range 2.41–2.62 (Table 3). It is well known that the value of g is less than 2.003 for transition metal com-

Table 3. Electronic and EPR spectral data of complexes

Complexes	ν_1 (cm ⁻¹)	ν_2 (cm ⁻¹)	ν_3 (cm ⁻¹)	g_{iso}	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	G
[CoLCl ₂]	8772	18519	20000	2.41	-	-	-
[CoL(NO ₃) ₂]	8700	18100	20833	2.52	-	-	-
[CoL(SCN) ₂]	8761	18621	20650	2.62	-	-	-
[CuLCl ₂]	17241	-	-	-	2.26	2.07	3.71
[CuL(NO ₃) ₂]	14680	-	-	-	2.29	2.12	2.41
[CuL(SCN) ₂]	14650	-	-	-	2.27	2.09	3.33

plexes containing d -shell less than half filled, whereas g is greater than 2.003 for complexes containing d -shells more than half filled. The observed g values suggested that d -shell was more than half filled in Co^{II} complexes. The deviation of the g values from the free electron value (2.0023) may be due to interaction between the spin and orbital motion of the electron. This interaction prevents complete quenching of the orbital contribution. EPR spectra of Cu^{II} complexes were recorded at room temperature in the polycrystalline state, on X band at frequency of 9.1 GHz under the magnetic field strength of 3000G. The present Cu^{II} complexes exhibited well resolved anisotropic signals in the parallel and perpendicular regions. The

observed data showed that $g_{\parallel} = 2.26$ –2.29 and $g_{\perp} = 2.07$ –2.12 (Table 3).

Kivelson and Neiman have shown that g_{\parallel} is a moderately sensitive function for indicating covalency. Relatively speaking $g_{\parallel} > 2.3$ is characteristic of anionic environment and $g_{\parallel} < 2.3$ of a covalent environment in M-L bonding²⁴. The observed g_{\parallel} values were less than 2.3 and in agreement with the covalent character of the M-L bond. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2.0023$ was observed for the complexes indicated that unpaired electron was localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the Cu^{II} ion²³. Thus a tetragonal geometry was proposed for the aforesaid complexes. $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measure the exchange interaction between the metal centres in a polycrystalline solid has been calculated. According to Hathaway²⁴ if $G > 4$ the exchange interaction is negligible and if $G < 4$ indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The reported complexes showed G value < 4 indicating the exchange interaction in complexes.

EIMS mass spectra :

The electronic impact mass spectrum of the Co^{II} chloro complex showed a molecular ion [CoC₂₀H₂₀N₄Cl₂]⁺ peak at m/z 447 amu, since the calculated mass of this complex was 446 amu therefore the molecular ion peak may be corresponding to M⁺ + 1 isotopic peak. Cu^{II} nitrate complex showed molecular ion [CuC₂₀H₂₀N₆O₆]⁺ peak at m/z 503 amu. The observed data indicated the monomeric nature and confirmed the proposed formulae for the complexes.

Electrochemical studies :

The electrochemical study was carried out in DMF solution and a three electrode system was used in experiment. A glassy carbon electrode was employed as working electrode, an Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and a platinum wire as auxiliary electrode. CV obtained at a scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹ in the +0.5 to -1.8 V potential range. The complex [CuLCl₂] showed well defined cathodic and anodic peaks with peak potential $E_{\text{pc}} = -0.286$ V, $E_{\text{pa}} = -0.396$ V (vs Ag/AgCl). The oxidation and reduction peak separation was 85 mV within the scan range used. The ratio of oxidation peak current I_{pa} to the reduction peak current I_{pc} was approximately equal to one. It indicated that this redox reaction was quasi-re-

versible one electron process^{25,26}. The half wave potential $E_{1/2}$ was calculated by using the formula reported²⁷, and was found to be -0.341 V.

Thermal analysis :

Thermogravimetric and differential thermal analysis of some reported complexes were carried out in the temperature range $50-70$ °C. The TG curves of $[\text{CuLCl}_2]$ and $[\text{CuL}(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ complexes clearly indicated the absence of water molecules inside or outside the coordination sphere as no significant mass loss observed up to $120-150$ °C. The decomposition of organic part of these complexes started around 250 °C as indicated by major fall in the % weight loss. Finally, complexes converted into their metal oxides as end product around 650 °C. The conversion of complexes into metal oxide has been found in accordance with the proposed formulae for the complexes.

Conclusions :

New cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes of dibenzo-[*b,g*]-5,6,11,12-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododeca-4,7-10,12-tetraene macrocyclic ligand have been prepared and characterized by various physico-chemical techniques. Spectral studies indicated that the complexes have six coordinated octahedral environment. Magnetic susceptibility measurements support the high spin nature of reported complexes. EPR data of copper(II) complexes showed that unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The cyclic voltammogram of chloro complex of copper showed a pair of quasi-reversible peaks.

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References

1. D. P. Singh, V. Malik and R. Kumar, *Res. Lett. Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, Article ID 824561, 4 pages.
2. M. Fernandez, R. Batista and A. Macias, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 783.
3. M. Shakir, P. Chingsubam, H. T. N. Chishti, Y. Azim and N. Begum, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **43**, 556.
4. S. Chandra and S. D. Sharma, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2002, **27**, 732.
5. S. Chandra and S. Sharma, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 150.
6. A. Chaudhary, N. Bansal, A. Gajraj and R. V. Singh, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003, **96**, 393.
7. D. P. Singh, R. Kumar, V. Malik and P. Tyagi, *J. Enzym. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **22**, 177.
8. S. Chandra and R. Kumar, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2005, **61**, 437.
9. S. Chandra and Sangeetika, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 1629.
10. J. Seto, S. Tamura, N. Asai and N. Kishii, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1996, **68**, 1429.
11. D. S. Kumar and V. Alexander, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1995, **238**, 63.
12. S. Chandra and U. Kumar, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2004, **60**, 2825.
13. R. Rajavel, M. Senthil and C. Anitha, *E. J. Chem.*, 2008, **5**, 620.
14. A. Reiss, S. Florea, T. Caproiu and N. Stanica, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2009, **33**, 775.
15. G. G. Mohamed, M. M. Omar and A. M. M. Hindy, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2005, **62**, 1140.
16. S. Chandra and U. Kumar, *J. Saudi. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **8**, 77.
17. M. Joseph, A. Sreekanth, V. Suni and M. R. P. Kurup, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2006, **64**, 637.
18. S. Chandra and U. Kumar, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2005, **61**, 219.
19. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, USA, 1986.
20. S. Chandra, S. D. Sharma and U. Kumar, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2004, **34**, 75.
21. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
22. S. Chandra and A. Kumar, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2007, **66**, 1347.
23. D. N. Kumar, B. K. Singh, B. S. Garg and P. K. Singh, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2003, **59**, 1487.
24. B. J. Hathaway, J. N. Bardley and R. D. Gillard, "Essays in Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, USA, 1971.
25. H. B. Sheng, L. H. Kuai, L. H. Ni and J. Y. Li, *J. Chinese Rare Earth Soc.*, 1997, **15**, 182.
26. A. S. Kumbhar, S. B. Padhye, D. X. West and A. E. Liberta, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1991, **16**, 276.
27. Q. U. Chen, Q. H. Luo, D. G. Fu and J. T. Chen, *J. Chem. Sci., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2873.

